

ENHANCING NUMERACY SKILLS TOWARDS INTERVENTION PLAN OF KINDERGARTEN LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the critical role of numeracy skills in the early education of kindergarten learners in the Philippines. It investigates the assessment and teaching strategies employed by kindergarten teachers, with a focus on both teacher-directed and student-directed play-based instruction. The research also examines the challenges faced by educators in promoting numeracy skills. The findings underscore the significance of play-based learning in kindergarten education and emphasize the need for continuous professional development and intervention plans to enhance numeracy instruction. The study offers valuable insights for educators and policymakers aiming to improve the quality of early mathematics education.

Keywords: *Numeracy skills, kindergarten learners, play-based learning, teacher-directed, student-directed, intervention plan, early mathematics education*

INTRODUCTION

Learning in the basic education is regarded as the most crucial stage of learning and development stages of a learner. It is where the basic essential skills are introduced so as with reading, writing and arithmetic. In the Philippines, the basic education curriculum starts with a compulsory kindergarten education as promulgated by the Republic Act 10157, or "The Kindergarten Education Act" made Kindergarten the compulsory and mandatory entry stage to basic education. Section 2 of this Act provides that all five (5)-year old children shall be given equal opportunities for Kindergarten Education to effectively promote their physical, social, emotional, and intellectual development, including values formation, so they will be ready for school. The Department of Education (DepEd) believes that Kindergarten is the transition period from informal to formal literacy (Grades 1–12), considering that age five (5) is within the critical years in which positive experiences must be nurtured to ascertain school readiness.

Meanwhile, numeracy skills are considered as a complex skill that a learner should develop in their formation years as early as in the kindergarten. As regards with the kindergarten curriculum, numeracy skills are being developed in the mathematics area as part of the Kindergarten Curriculum Framework (KCF). As part of honing learners with their preparatory skills in gaining holistic development, Children are required to grasp and display knowledge, thinking skills, and insights about mathematical patterns, notions of numbers, length, capacity, mass, and time via the use of real objects or materials, and to apply these to their everyday experiences in a meaningful way. Children are presented with a variety of manipulative exercises to assist them in recognizing linkages and interconnections in mathematics and allow them to cope with mathematical concepts and ideas with flexibility.

Furthermore, according to PISA result 2021 or Program for International Student Assessment, the organization assessing the quality of education in various countries participating on the said evaluation, the Philippines ranked as second lowest in Mathematics and Science. In Mathematics literacy, the average score for the Philippines was 353 versus 489 for the OECD average (Luz, 2022). These results is very alarming which may cause a great effect to the education system of the country. Knowing the fact that numeracy skills can only be developed through rigid and quality mathematics instruction, there is a need to provide enhancement of the teaching instruction in the primary level. Thus, this scenario calls for an assessment of the present numeracy skills instruction in the kindergarten level as it is the first stage of learning in the basic education curriculum in the Philippines.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess numeracy skills of kindergarten learners in the Division of Batangas.

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of length of service?
2. How do the respondents assess their Numeracy instruction as to:
 - 2.1 teacher directed play; and
 - 2.2 child directed play?
3. What are the challenges that teachers face when teaching numeracy to kindergarten students?
4. Is there significant difference among the respondents' assessment on their numeracy instruction when grouped according to profile variables?
5. Based on the findings, what intervention plan may be proposed to enhance the numeracy skills of the kindergarten students?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized descriptive research design to determine the Numeracy Skills of Kindergarten Learners. This design was deemed to be the most appropriate to analyze and interpret the data to be collected during the research period. The process of descriptive research goes beyond the mere collection and tabulation of information and data. It involves the interpretation of the meaning of what is described.

The survey questionnaire was the primary tool for gathering data in this study. The researcher used books, publications, as well as the internet, to supplement and improve the knowledge collected. Seeking some advice from research experts and browsing the internet and

substantiating the information will be considered. Likewise, the approved tool went to Cronbach's Alpha for reliability testing.

The first section determined the demographic profile of respondents. Also, a researcher made questionnaire will be used in the study.

RESULTS

Table 1
Teacher Directed

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In my math class, I... set clear objectives and goals every topic	3.70	Very Great Extent
Provide clear examples for each of the math concepts being taught	3.67	Very Great Extent
Employ various pedagogical strategies such as direct, indirect approach and guided instruction	3.48	Great Extent
Explain the concepts from simple to complex	3.59	Very Great Extent
Maximize learning opportunities through real-world tasks where application of mathematical concepts are seen	3.37	Great Extent
Provide differentiated instruction to cater various needs and skills of the students	3.56	Very Great Extent
Assign additional activities to develop mastery of the students towards the topic being discussed	3.59	Very Great Extent
use gamified activities to ensure engagement among the students	3.41	Great Extent
Integrate concepts within and among other content areas curriculum	3.52	Very Great Extent
Utilize various digital technology to enhance learning	3.00	Great Extent
Composite Mean	3.49	Great Extent

Table 2
Student Directed

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
In my math class, I... Understand the lesson through experiential learning	3.37	Great Extent
Try to solve problems through interactive discussion among peers and tutoring activities	3.19	Great Extent
Explain their ways on how to arrive with a correct answer	3.30	Great Extent
Discuss mathematical ideas, problems, solutions, or methods in pairs or small groups	3.30	Great Extent
Write extended explanations of mathematical ideas, solutions, or methods	3.41	Great Extent

Work on a mathematics investigation, problem, or project for several days	3.11	Great Extent
Do boardwork and let them explain to the class their answer	3.48	Great Extent
Think and made it public (Structuring Mathematical Student Talk (public to the small group)	3.07	Great Extent
engage with each other's thinking through collaborative discussions	3.19	Great Extent
Conduct sense-making, conjecturing, and justifying drive the instruction	3.30	Great Extent
Composite Mean	3.27	Great Extent

Table 3
Significant Difference of the Numeracy Instruction when Grouped according to Profile Variables

Variables	p-value	f-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Length of Service				
Teacher-Directed	0.071544	3.027998	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Student Directed	4.29E-08	3.027998	Reject Ho	Significant
Educational Background				
Teacher-Directed	0.678108	3.402829	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Student Directed	0.312382	3.422132	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 4
Challenges Encountered by the teachers when teaching numeracy skills in the Kindergarten

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Mistakes such as number additions, substitutions, transpositions, omissions, and reversals in writing, reading, and recalling numbers.	3.23	Great Extent
Slowness in understanding math concepts in word problems.	3.51	Very Great Extent
Limited strategic planning ability.	3.40	Great Extent
Difficulty remembering math facts, concepts, rules, formulas, sequences, and procedures.	3.49	Great Extent
Inability to visualize; appearing absentminded or lost in thought.	3.56	Very Great Extent
Difficulty following sequential procedures and directions in math steps.	3.37	Great Extent
Confusing operations signs or performing them in wrong order.	3.28	Great Extent
Composite Mean	3.41	Great Extent

DISCUSSION

Table 1-It can be gleaned from the table that the respondents assessed teacher-directed play as their numeracy instruction to a great extent, with a composite mean of 3.49. The indicator 'In my math class, I set clear objectives and goals for every topic', has the highest mean of 3.70. Meanwhile, the indicator 'In my math class, I provide clear examples for each of the math concepts being taught' came in second with a mean of 3.67. However, the indicators 'In my math class, I explain the concepts from simple to complex and assign additional activities to develop the student's mastery of the topic being discussed' came in third with a mean of 3.59.

The findings revealed that teachers kept going with play-based activities that made it clear what they wanted the kids to learn and gave them examples of questions they could ask to fit the kids' growing understanding. It was a collaborative and iterative process. Reviewing the goals of each task helped the teachers understand the math concepts behind them and made it easier for them to tell when the kids had met the learning goals. Also, kindergarten teachers were better ready to implement child centered practice by providing a variety of play-based activities that were relevant and attractive to the children, as well as supporting instructions, prompts, and recommendations for extending activities.

As revealed from the results, Kindergarten teachers have the opportunity to make learning more interesting and interactive for their students by facilitating opportunities for guided play, exploration, interactions, and dialogues. Play-based learning, and more specifically teacher involvement in guided play, has been found to be the most developmentally appropriate method for teaching young children, although there are many different ways an early childhood educator could approach teaching. As an educational strategy, play-based learning has been shown to be highly effective. These findings coincide with research by Gettinger et al. (2011) which found that teachers tend to run their classrooms according to their own set of guidelines and expectations. All students in a teacher-led class work on the same activities with the same teacher, and the focus is on getting the right answers rather than on learning anything meaningful from the experience. Teacher-led methods, such as drill and practice and tight classroom rules, may be helpful for children with low academic skills or issues staying focused on learning activities, as indicated by Kikas et al. (2014).

Table 2- It can be seen from the table that the respondents assessed student-directed play as their numeracy instruction to a great extent, with a composite mean of 3.27. The indicator 'In my math class, I do board work and let them explain to the class their answer', has the highest mean of 3.48. Meanwhile, the indicator 'In my math class, I write extended explanations of mathematical ideas, solutions, or methods' came in second with a mean of 3.41. However, the indicator 'In my math class, I understand the lesson through experiential learning' came in third with a mean of 3.37. The findings suggest that kindergarten learners can learn math concepts through fun and engaging child-directed play. Teachers can encourage children's active exploration of mathematical ideas by creating a safe and fun space for play during math class.

Similarly, they can inspire kids to construct freely, sort, pattern, and count with these materials. A kindergartener's natural curiosity and love of mathematics can be nurtured through engaging

and relevant activities that incorporate math concepts, such as problem-solving stations or activity centers where children can work on math puzzles, challenges, and hands-on activities independently or in small groups.

The amount of time children spends doing things they choose can improve the number and quality of interactions between teachers and kids, which can make kids less likely to act out. Hur, Buettner, and Jeon's (2015) study showed that teachers who believe more in a child-centered curriculum than those who believe more in a teacher-centered curriculum have students who are better at self-regulation. One reason for this could be that, according to Williford et al. (2013), the quality of interactions between teachers and children is better when the activities are child-centered. Even though it's not clear what causes what, there is a link between how well teachers and kids get along and how well kids are able to control themselves. Williford et al. (2013) found that when children oversee their own learning, they are more likely to be interested in the tasks and to interact with their teachers.

Table 3-This table shows the Significant Difference of the Numeracy Instruction when grouped according to Profile Variables. It can be gleaned in the table above that in terms of Length of Service specifically in teacher-directed, f value is greater than p value which result failed to reject Ho. In other words, it is not significant. For the student directed the p-value is greater than the f-value which result to reject Ho. It means that it is significant.

Moreover, for educational background the f value is higher than p-value which means that the teacher-directed is not significant since it failed to reject ho. For student directed, the f-value is higher than the p-value which means that the decision is failed to reject ho which has a verbal interpretation of not significant.

In connection with this, few studies have been conducted in South Africa on the use of visual tools that sought to explore teachers' understanding and use of visual objects in teaching numeracy, amongst which are studies conducted by Wilmont and Schafer (2015) and Mntunjani, Adendorff and Siyepu (2018). Based on these sentiments about the importance of visual tools in teaching numeracy, teachers' understanding, and use of visual tools are essential to instruct numeracy in the Foundation Phase.

As a matter of fact, Barmby et al. (2017) were of the view that the use of visual tools is an essential part of teachers' knowledge of mathematics that could play an important role in the explanation of mathematical ideas. mathematical visualization is the process of forming images (mentally, or with pencil and paper, or with the aid of technology) and using such images effectively for mathematical discovery and understanding.

Table 4- The table above explains the challenges encountered by the teachers when teaching numeracy skills in the Kindergarten . Inability to visualize; appearing absentminded or lost in thought got the highest weighted mean of 3.56 which has a verbal interpretation of great extent.

In this regard, researchers like Alshatri, Wakil, Jamal and Bakhtyar (2019) believed that learners usually have difficulties in learning mathematics because of mathematics abstraction; therefore, visualizing numeracy has become a solution. Slowness in understanding math concepts in word problems is considered as the second highest which has a weighted mean of 3.51. It has a verbal interpretation of great extent.

In connection with this, A similar view on the significance of visual tools in facilitating learning in mathematics was expressed by Budaloo (2015), who argued that mathematics is a multimodal discourse where different modes of representation are necessary. This sentiment was supported by the findings of his study that revealed that all the participants in his study were actively engaged in using visual reasoning as a pedagogic practice in their mathematics classrooms.

Difficulty remembering math facts, concepts, rules, formulas, sequences, and procedures has a weights mean of 3.49 which signifies that it has a great extent. This has something to do with the study Wilmot and Schafer (2015) . In their study, it was revealed that because of the lack of training, teachers lacked knowledge of how visual arts could be used to teach the concepts of space and shape. To the Foundation Phase teachers' training of teaching numeracy should be added the awareness of how young children learn. They advised that teachers should be trained to build on the informal mathematical ideas' learners bring into the classroom from.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The length of time of the kindergarten teachers has been teaching and their educational background will be of great assistance in improving their numeracy instruction for learners in their class.
2. Teacher and child-directed play are significant to kindergarten teachers in their numeracy instruction.
3. It was evident that there were numerous challenges faced by the kindergarten teachers.
4. The respondents' assessment on their numeracy instruction when grouped according to profile variables is not that much important.
5. Intervention for students' enhancement is needed for their effective and efficient learning.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the collected data, the researcher recommends the following:

- 1.The school administrators should provide opportunities for kindergarten teachers to attend trainings on updated numeracy instruction to inspire them to adapt to the global trend of play-based learning.
- 2.The teachers should improve numeracy instruction by promoting play-based activities that allow learners to have repeated exposures to manipulatives, allowing them to build confidence, develop creativity, and learn needed competencies.
3. Teachers and parents must collaborate to assist kindergarten learners in bringing prior mathematical knowledge and connecting it with new learning in relevant ways.
- 4.Teachers should continuously incorporate teacher-directed and child-directed learning play into their numeracy instruction so that learners can make connections between what they have learned and their own experiences and interests.
- 5.The intervention plan may be used by kindergarten teachers to help their learners improve their numeracy skills. Further research must be conducted in the field of numeracy education to

\better understand the issues and challenges faced by educators and ultimately offer answers to these problems.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher hereby declares her commitment to upholding established ethical norms and principles within the context of her research. These principles include gaining informed permission from participants, safeguarding their privacy and confidentiality, and mitigating potential harm or risks. In addition, the open management of data, the acknowledgment of conflicts of interest, and the precise documentation of results are fundamental elements of ethical research. By adhering to these principles, not only are the rights and well-being of individuals participating upheld, but the overall ethical standing of the scientific community is also preserved. This, in turn, fosters public trust in research and its outcomes.

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